

**NEW TRENDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING
IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

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Annotation: As the world becomes ever more connected, the appeal of learning a new language is clear. Whether for business or pleasure, being able to communicate on an international level can bring many benefits. Nowadays most students of higher education want to use effective study methods so they can learn a language fast and speak it. So today English teachers of higher educations should be creative, searchable and find the best suitable method for each group or even for each student. In this article there are given some modern methods of teaching English.

Key words: approach, method, language learner, multilingual, Direct method, suggestopedia, lexical approach, structural approach

INTRODUCTION

The modernization of higher professional education dictates the search for new methods, techniques and technologies that would contribute to the effective teaching of students, including foreign languages. Modern education in order to achieve high educational results should be characterized by constant information content of the content of education, activation of the pace of learning with the involvement of modern information technologies. In modern scientific and

methodological literature, more and more attention is paid by the authors to the justification of the high educational potential and the effectiveness of the use of innovative teaching technologies in the system of teaching English in higher education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the present stage of development of higher professional education, there is a tendency to reduce the number of classroom hours and increase the hours allocated for independent work of students. In this regard, we can state the fact that today the role of the teacher in the educational process is being transformed. Until recently, the teacher was perceived as the main source of information, but today his role can be more fully characterized as the organizer and leader, expert and consultant of the educational and self-educational activities of future specialists.

Such transformations became possible due to the emergence and widespread introduction of innovative and more effective technologies, forms and means of education into the educational process of higher education, which make it possible to optimize the process of professional training of future specialists as part of their studies at the university.

The high productivity and efficiency of innovative technologies in the context of training future specialists is justified by their multifunctionality. Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies perform the following functions in the educational process: informative; formative; motivating; systematizing; controlling.

Innovative technologies and teaching methods make it possible to achieve the following goals: accessibility of the perception of educational material; systematization of knowledge; development of creative abilities of students; self-education; removing the psychological barrier (fear of communicating, making a mistake); comprehension of educational material, analysis of learned material.

To effective innovative pedagogical technologies that can be used in the system of teaching English in higher education with a high level of effectiveness in achieving educational results, researchers most often include interactive distance learning technologies (Skype, Viber, WhatsApp, e-mail, Internet chat, etc.). etc.),

computer learning tools (electronic manuals, textbooks, sources of virtual libraries, educational portals, etc.), multimedia learning resources, training and testing and other latest information technologies [1].

Tangible progress regarding the effectiveness of teaching English both in the humanities and in technical universities, according to researchers, has been achieved through the widespread use of electronic learning tools in the educational process of higher education. These tools are used both in the classroom and extracurricular (distance) learning.

The didactic potential of electronic teaching aids in English classes lies in the fact that their use in the educational process contributes to [2]:

- better assimilation of knowledge by students;
- the formation and development of various types of skills and abilities (listening skills based on adapted and authentic sound texts, the ability to reproduce monologue and dialogic speech, the skills and abilities of translation and summarizing texts, skills and reading skills with the direct use of materials from the Internet and local networks;
- increasing the informative richness and visibility of the lesson;
- expansion of active and passive dictionaries of students, familiarization with the vocabulary of modern English, which reproduces the culture of a certain country, its political and social structure;
- formation of creativity, development of creative activity of future specialists;
- the formation of motivation for the cognitive activity of students, the need to use a foreign language in interactive communication;
- strengthening the motivation of independent work of students;
- increasing the level of individualization and differentiation of students' activities;
- the ability to choose the pace and volume of educational material, the level of its complexity, to implement control with feedback and diagnostics, to increase the level of its objectivity.

At the present stage, the leading information technology, the means of which are used in almost all spheres of human life, is the Internet. Internet resources not only provide a number of additional means of implementing interpersonal and international communication, but also provide new opportunities in the field of education. Within the framework of this technology, the education system uses information sites and portals, educational programs on electronic media, the ability to obtain information, implement consulting and control knowledge remotely via e-mail, online conferences and video classes.

The advantages of the Internet as an innovative learning tool are due to the fact that it is an unlimited source of information, which allows both the teacher and students to save time searching for the necessary material (theoretical, textual, sound, visual information, etc.); provides great opportunities for creativity in terms of developing didactic material, forms and types of work, individual and group tasks, projects; allows you to increase the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language due to the possibility of total immersion in the language material and increasing the motivation of students to learn [4].

The use of innovative learning technologies in the system of teaching English at a university makes it possible to make a transition from the subject principle of constructing content to the creation of integrated training courses that reflect a holistic picture of professional activity, to change the nature of knowledge itself, which in the context of such interactive learning is transformed into the category of "knowledge for activity". ". In other words, within the framework of such training, the knowledge of future specialists act as functions and means of solving specific professional problems.

The use of innovative teaching aids brings changes in the organizational structure of the educational process: the requirements for the methods and forms of organizing the teaching of foreign languages are changing - active and interactive individual and group forms of working with educational material become leading.

In the context of building classes based on the use of innovative technologies and teaching aids, the type of activity and the nature of the relationship between the

teacher and students are changing. The role of the student turns into an active cognitive position, while the teacher, in turn, acts as a coordinator, consultant, partner.

Finally, of course, mobile language learning also includes real-life apps, since these can be used for authentic language learning. For example, one can use the Twitter or Facebook apps to read native speakers' posts and communicate with them, or listen to the radio from any country where the second language is spoken. One can also watch a TV show on Netflix or shorter clips on YouTube. The important factor for second language learning is how these resources from Netflix or YouTube are used as learner materials, and whether the instructional design is effective in strengthening language learning.

All of these apps have pervaded the language learning field worldwide. Duolingo is a free language learning platform that enables strengthening of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation in 28 languages, and has more than 100 million users in 2018. (Usai et.al, 2018) [6]. Gamification tools such as Kahoot, which can be applied to any subject matter, including languages, have more than 70 million users and are used actively in foreign language classrooms. (Wang, 2018). Other notable tools with high volume language learning users are the online versions of Rosetta Stone and digital flashcards such as Quizlet. These new technologies signal a radical change in the instructor-learner relationship. Given the easy access to these tools, learners have much more control and can drive how their learning happens, without being directed by the authority figure of a teacher in the classroom. This shift has empowered learners to be more autonomous and to operate digitally within learning communities that go beyond the traditional classroom [7].

Summarizing the above, we conclude that, along with the indicated advantages of the analyzed learning technologies, the importance of academic forms of obtaining knowledge and developing students' competencies should not be leveled. The use of modern technologies in English classes should not be an end in itself. These technologies should be perceived as effective didactic and technical teaching aids.

CONCLUSION

To conclude teaching a language can help in both your personal and professional life. It can boost other skills and improve your cultural understanding. Each student has unique talent, interest in learning a new language. So, a professional teacher should find the most suitable effective methods of teaching a foreign language according to student's own desire, capability and time.

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